

REPORT OF THE
**2020 Science Europe
High Level Workshop on ERA**

THE ERA CONTRIBUTION TO THE POST-COVID-19 RECOVERY
AND TRANSITION TO A RESILIENT SOCIETY

18 NOVEMBER 2020, LISBON

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Introduction

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, Europe faces extraordinary health, economic, and social challenges. As part of its response, the European Commission launched a recovery plan on 27 May 2020 to address the long-term impact of the pandemic, alongside a revised proposal for the 2021–2027 Multiannual Financial Framework. In addition, it adopted a new Communication and Roadmap on the European Research Area (ERA) on 30 September 2020.

A key challenge for both the ERA and research and innovation in general will be to address the consequences of the pandemic, to strengthen societal resilience, improve crisis preparedness, and enable an efficient response. While there is a need to update the narrative and objectives of ERA that were set in 2012, its main goals remain: strengthened national research systems in all Member States, Open Science, improved researcher careers, creation of an open labour market for researchers, improved gender balance, and a better performing research and innovation system across Europe.

The 2020 edition of the Science Europe High Level Workshop on ERA was co-hosted with the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) and the Portuguese Ministry of Science, Technology, and Higher Education (MCTES). It explored how research and innovation can contribute to crisis recovery and to societal resilience, in the context of an evolving research culture.

Workshop participants, including heads of national research organisations and senior representatives of national ministries and EU institutions, discussed ways to improve research culture. The main focus of the discussions was on the conditions needed across Europe for researcher mobility, Open Science, and research collaboration to continue building an effective ERA.

The outcomes of this workshop will contribute to the implementation of the R&I policy priorities of the German Presidency of the EU Council (including the anticipated Council Conclusions on ERA), and inform those of the following Portuguese and Slovenian presidencies.

The High Level Workshop on ERA took place on 18 November 2020 as a virtual event.

High Level Workshop on ERA

Welcome Address

Keynote Speech

/ **Manuel Heitor**, Minister for Science, Technology, and Higher Education, Portugal

During his welcome address, **Minister Heitor** presented three elements that will be crucial for research to contribute to building more resilient societies.

Firstly, science and technological knowledge need to be translated into the economy to create employment. In this context, synergies between national programmes and European programmes are essential, including with the [NextGenerationEU](#) recovery fund. The role of funding agencies is crucial to ensure these synergies.

Secondly, open and collaborative research needs to be fostered to overcome all types of borders and to address the problems of the Anthropocene. Zoonotic diseases are increasing because of the excessive impact of human activity on our natural environment, such as climate change. A key challenge will be for humanity to better balance economic activity and the protection of the ecosystem. To that end, more research is needed to better understand the relationship between and impact of human activity on the environment, and to determine how to protect the latter.

Last but not least, better research careers are needed to avoid that researchers leave Europe for other areas of the world. Instead, Europe must be able to attract and retain scientists. Against this backdrop, for example, the European Research Council should be strengthened, with recruitments that are better co-ordinated across countries.

Session 1: New Challenges for Research Mobility and Career Development

Keynote Speech

/ **Professor Dame Ottoline Leyser**, Chief Executive, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)

In her keynote speech, **Professor Dame Ottoline Leyser** emphasised the need to re-conceptualise the research process by including a wider set of activities to which a variety of people with different roles and skillsets contribute. These include training and mentoring, co-creating programmes with the public, and the work of technicians. The belief that research is the product of brilliant minds making ground-breaking discoveries alone creates both a divide between science and society, and generates undue pressure on researchers and innovators.

There needs to be a shift towards a more inclusive research ecosystem that rewards all relevant contributions to the research process. More people need to be brought into the system of science, and, to that end, more fluid careers have to be supported, enabling swift movement within and in and out of the research system.

Main messages from the panel

Moderator: **Angelika Kalt**, Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF), Switzerland

/ **Ricardo Conde**, President of the Portugal Space Agency, Portugal

/ **Rosa Menéndez**, President of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC), Spain

/ **Miriam Van Hoed**, IDEA Consult (MORE4 study), Belgium

MOBILITY BETWEEN THE PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR

It is well established that economic growth and the competitiveness of any given country is associated with its investment in research and development. However, while the focus is often on publicly funded research, **Ricardo Conde** argued that private companies account for approximately two thirds of the total R&D investment. In fact, a large number of researchers work in enterprises on a wide variety of topics, such as biomedical, pharmaceutical, biotechnology, hardware, materials, software, or space research. It is crucial to better integrate the private and public research ecosystems and foster public-private co-operation where relevant.

MOVEMENT OF RESEARCHERS AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

Panellists agreed that the COVID-19 pandemic is complicating researchers' mobility. **Miriam Van Hoed** indicated that there is evidence in the MORE4 study that short-term mobility can, to some extent, be replaced by virtual exchange. In the current context these forms of exchange will become more common than before. Virtual mobility can also stimulate interaction with groups of researchers that are less open to physical mobility and can as such be conducive to positive career outcomes for researchers. A challenge is the recognition of virtual mobility in research careers. However, drawing on the experience at CSIC, **Rosa Menéndez** expressed concerns that virtual mobility could mostly benefit researchers in well-established networks, and would not be so positive for early-career researchers.

Following the COVID-19 crisis, it is likely that researchers' mobility patterns will change permanently. New concepts of what mobility is and how researchers can move across borders need to be developed. Panellists emphasised that digital mobility must be supported, including through the development of appropriate digital infrastructure and the promotion of new skills that enable different career paths, such as those related to the management and curation of data, as well as the digitalisation of infrastructures and research processes.

Discussions

To help incentivise the necessary changes to the research ecosystem, **Ottoline Leyser** said that there needs to be a move away from putting too much value on scientific publications, and to develop a wider range of ways to assess research. For instance, a lot of high-quality research conducted by industry does not result in publications. Similarly, careful attention should be given to the development of CV formats. UKRI is currently finalising a template for a 'narrative CV' for researchers. Participants emphasised that intersectoral mobility must be promoted and duly recognised as a merit for career progression.

Ricardo Conde stressed that a pragmatic approach is essential when looking at how movement and co-operation between the private and public sectors can be stimulated. Companies can spend up to 20% of their income in R&D but the investment is focused on developing products for market. Reflecting on the ERA's objective to translate R&I results into the economy, panellists wondered if, instead of structures for the transfer of knowledge, spaces of public-private co-creation could be sustained through the promotion of intersectoral mobility.

A good example of a platform that stimulate collaboration between research and researchers, stakeholders and the general public is vTaiwan, which could be adapted and combine a variety of online tools and machine learning.

Session 2: The European Research Area: Breaking the Silos

Keynote Speech

/ **Helena Pereira**, President of the Board of Directors of the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), Portugal

Helena Pereira recalled that the ERA was launched in 2000 during the first Portuguese Presidency of the Council of the European Union. At the time, the main objective was to de-fragment the European research ecosystem. She emphasised that, currently, the ERA's objective is to develop the full potential of research and innovation, and thus contribute more and better to society, growth, and employment. In this context, it will be essential to further support the development of the relevant skills and competences needed to tackle the current societal challenges.

She highlighted the main silos of the European research ecosystem: between disciplines, public and private sector, national borders, and science and society. To break down the barriers between silos, it will be necessary, across Europe, to develop new ways to assess research, strengthen researchers' transversal and digital skills, support fundamental research, protect academic freedom, increase diversity and combat inequality in the research ecosystem.

Regarding bureaucracy as another silo in the ecosystem, Helena Pereira concluded that the simplification of calls and funding instruments would support breaking down the barriers.

Main messages from the panel

Moderator: **Ingrid Petersson**, Director General of FORMAS, Sweden

- / **Zbigniew Błocki**, Director of the Polish National Science Centre (NCN), Poland
- / **Berthold Neizert**, Head of the Department of Research Policy and International Relations of the Max Planck Society (MPG), Germany
- / **Thierry Damerval**, President of the French National Research Agency (ANR), France

International collaboration

An essential element of a well-functioning European research ecosystem is the promotion of co-operation among organisations, including between Research Funding Organisations at international level. **Zbigniew Błocki** highlighted that cross-border collaboration is crucial to addressing the lack of mobility within research systems in lower-performing countries. In Poland, the National Science Centre has established various strong partnerships, such as with the Max Planck Society to create excellence centres and is co-ordinating the only two ERA-Nets that are co-ordinated by a EU-13 country.

International collaboration is a key feature of the ERA and an essential prerequisite for successful science, thus strengthening the innovation base. **Berthold Neizert** stressed that interdisciplinarity must be enhanced to break academic silos of different research disciplines concomitant with overcoming structural limitations of research organisations. Finally, 'breaking the silos' is an expression of freedom of research. This freedom and its value for the ERA has currently been commemorated in the '[Bonn Declaration on Freedom of Scientific Research](#)'.

Open Science

While there has been an unprecedented move towards Open Science in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is unclear whether this will result in long-lasting changes in publication practices.

Thierry Damerval mentioned the results of a recent survey ([The Academic Response to COVID-19](#), *Frontiers Public Health*, 28 October 2020), which found that half of the respondents said they would not change the way they publish their research. This indicates that the Open Science practices implemented during the response to the pandemic might not be translated into increased openness in the research ecosystem. Additionally, stronger controls must be developed to ensure that Open Science does not translate to the wide dissemination of data and results without proper peer review or respect for fundamental rights and deontology.

Open Science needs to be as inclusive of research disciplines as possible, and social sciences and humanities must be included. It also must be responsive to the needs of researchers and society.

Discussions

Panellists raised the issues of the management of pre-prints, preliminary results, and building citizens' trust in research when the scientific process occurs in the open. More rigour and control are needed from the scientific community, based on peer review, quality control, and the use of adequate data management plans. Efforts should be made to strengthen the communication skills of researchers as well as on the ethical behaviour of researchers in the scientific process. Moreover, ensuring the ethical communication of research processes and results entails a collective responsibility to ensure that those who are invited to discuss them are the actual experts.

They highlighted that it should be more clearly explained to the general public that research is a process that aims to 'only' deliver scientific knowledge, and that it is the task of politicians and elected officials to take decisions that affect society. The speakers stressed that a key issue to be highlighted is that research, as any process of discovery, deals with uncertainty, while policy makers and the public look for certainty and answers. In sum, a broader understanding of the process of doing research and the pursuit of knowledge in and for society must be developed and communicated.

As such, medical research could provide a useful example as it is driven towards the needs of patients and society, which calls for interdisciplinary approaches. It also requires raising awareness among the public on the process of research and how research results can be interpreted. Additionally, researchers need to take into account the views of citizens in the definition of the direction of their research. These two proposals translate into the need to set up more platforms to facilitate collaboration and co-creation between researchers and the general public. It was highlighted that research has a responsibility to civil society to both disseminate its output in plain language and in a way that is recognisable to the public in their own lives.

Session 3: High level panel discussion

Roundtable discussion on research policies for a more resilient European society

Moderator: **Lidia Borrell-Damián**, Secretary General of Science Europe

- / **Mariya Gabriel**, European Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth
- / **Jure Gašparič**, State Secretary of Education, Science and Sport, Slovenia
- / **Karina Angelieva**, Deputy Minister of Science and Education, Bulgaria
- / **Dragoș Ciuparu**, State Secretary, Ministry of Education and Research, Romania
- / **Aase Marthe Horrigmo**, State Secretary, Ministry of Research and Higher Education, Norway
- / **Martina Hirayama**, State Secretary for Education, Research and Innovation, Switzerland
- / **Barbara Weitgruber**, Director General for Scientific Research and International Relations, Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, Austria
- / **Wilfried Kraus**, Deputy Director General for European Co-operation at the Federal Ministry for Education and Research, Germany
- / **Manuel Heitor**, Minister for Science, Technology, and Higher Education, Portugal
- / **Marc Schiltz**, President of Science Europe

Commissioner Gabriel highlighted that, in revising the ERA, the European Commission aimed to establish a level playing field within the research ecosystem, especially through the creation of the best possible conditions for co-operation and accessing research infrastructure across Europe. Persistent problems need to be addressed, such as the transfer of research results and innovation to industry, attracting more talent to science careers, and the fragmentation between geographical and disciplinary borders. To tackle this, the Commission will set up an 'ERA Forum for Transition' that will allow Member States, with support from the Commission, to co-ordinate strategies and agendas, and indicate areas and gaps for which to jointly develop priority actions. It will also propose a 'Pact for Research and Innovation' in 2021 to pool the collective responsibility of Member States, the EU, and stakeholders.

While the ERA can contribute to overcoming the COVID-19 pandemic, **Jure Gašparič** argued that it needs strong political and financial support and an inclusive and effective governance framework to make sure we deliver together on our common goals. He stressed a series of key requirements for success: the involvement of stakeholders, the co-design of cross-sectoral policies, and national input to its implementation. A paradigm shift is needed in how Europe works together and co-ordinates action at European and national levels. To achieve this, there must be stronger synchronisation of investments and policy changes. This requires meaningful interactions between stakeholders and policy makers. Funding agencies need flexibility, trust, and support for fundamental research to be resilient.

International collaboration will be crucial to enable a more collaborative approach to the prioritisation of investments in research. Supporting the full spectrum of research, according to **Karina Angelieva**, also relies on improving the system of co-ordination with stakeholders and European and national funders. Research career paths could similarly be better co-ordinated, for example by making use of Erasmus and regional bodies. She highlighted the importance of research infrastructure and data sharing and standards.

Dragoș Ciuparu recalled that resilience is not a new concept, but a way to develop the ideas and tools to manage crisis situations. Focusing on the ERA is essential to move towards more resilient societies. Against this backdrop, the following elements should be reinforced: 'brain balance' in the area of higher education and training for talents; improving the governance of

pan-European research infrastructures and revisiting ERIC regulation to create more inclusive and largely distributed networks; strengthening the research dimension of sectoral policies, especially revisiting the EU Industrial Strategy and IPCEI instrument; fostering EU cohesion policy and synergy with other relevant EU programmes; and cross-border collaboration to develop innovative projects and co-ordinate scientific efforts. Doing so requires measures to address regional disparities and the risk of increased geographical concentration of technology development. As a result, more joint programming and co-design are needed, as well as a strategic approach for improving the inclusiveness of the ERA.

Open international collaboration in research is essential to build an ERA that puts excellence at its core. Global crises, like the COVID-19 pandemic, require a common agenda between Member States and Associated Countries for global solutions. Mobilising national actors, from sector-ministries to industry and the public sector, should be the basis. Horizon Europe, in particular, needs an ambitious vision on how to collaborate with non-European partners. For **Aase Marthe Hørrigmo**, to make Europe a world leader in resilience, focus on the [Sustainable Development Goals](#), the [Green Deal](#), and the [Digital Agenda](#) are crucial. To that end, the whole Horizon Europe programme must be supported, especially the parts that address grand challenges, missions, and partnerships, as well as the co-operation with the Erasmus+ programme. EU instruments must also support collaboration with and mobility across business and industry, and recognise the role of students, who are crucial as citizens, the future workforce, and innovators, as well as the next generation of researchers. The recognition and reward processes for researchers are crucial for the development of knowledge and for knowledge sharing. A variety of skills and competences, including Open Science and mobility should be rewarded in academia and be included in the further development of the [EURAXESS-portal](#) and [European Charter and Code for Researchers](#).

Martina Hirayama stressed that the COVID-19 pandemic showed the strengths and weaknesses of the ERA. Indeed, excellence-based, curiosity-driven, and mission-oriented research can contribute to addressing crises. In the context of a mission-driven focus, it is essential to intensify trans- and cross-disciplinary research on pandemic prevention and impact, including not only health, but also fields such as social and digital sciences. In order to prepare for and address crises, citizens need to be involved, for instance through consultations that in turn, would increase the public trust in policy making. She concluded that, to identify research topics and translate findings into policy, flexible ad hoc groups could be set up.

Investment in blue-sky research is key to developing solutions to crises and prepare for the future unknowns. Vaccines, for example, are based on cutting-edge fundamental research over many years. **Barbara Weitgruber** highlighted the importance of sharing scientific results and sharing them quickly. She stressed that the COVID-19 pandemic raised awareness on the need for Open Science, addressing the relative inefficiency of traditional publication modes in such emergency circumstances, and implementing new methods of assessment. To build European resilience, interdisciplinary research and co-designing mission-oriented programmes are needed.

Wilfried Kraus said that resilience is a central issue for the German Presidency of the Council of the EU. Research is needed for all related policy questions, including SSH related topics such as demographics and migration. It is crucial that Europe maintains its technological sovereignty and is able to compete globally, in particular on Artificial Intelligence or quantum technology. But building resilience is also linked to preserving common European values. Actions are needed with all relevant stakeholders from all sectors. In this context, the 'Bonn Declaration on Freedom of Scientific Research' was adopted under the German Presidency, on 20 October 2020. He stressed that there is also a need to set up a monitoring system for academic freedom. Lastly, engaging

with citizens is crucial to successful science-based policy making, and to better communicate the importance of the ERA to the general public.

Manuel Heitor emphasised that there are strong links between research and education, as well as the importance of open collaboration in research. Progress has been achieved towards better co-operation between national and European research agencies. He considers the new NextGenerationEU financial instrument useful to further foster this co-operation. Additionally, the articulation of national funds with structural funds and Horizon Europe should be reinforced. He further stressed that support should be increased across all research disciplines as there is not enough knowledge to address societal challenges. Research careers should also be better promoted, including through Europe-wide recruitment and careers frameworks.

Marc Schiltz highlighted that, in the context of the current crisis, society expects research to contribute to the development of rapid solutions and that this has created additional challenges for researchers to communicate with society. To address these issues, a healthy research framework system is needed, based on international collaboration and academic freedom. He added that international and cross-sectoral collaboration and Open Science should be further promoted, and that data and digitalisation provide unprecedented possibilities for research to address complex problems. Overall, a new research system is needed that embodies a new culture in which everyone can contribute: locally, regionally, and internationally. That will make the ERA the most attractive area for researchers to engage in this enterprise of research and innovation.

Discussions

Panellists discussed potential key performance indicators to measure the evolution and progress of ERA. The [European Semester](#) was indicated as one potential instrument that could be used to that effect.

It was also discussed that more interaction between science and society was needed to combat the occurrence of mistrust in science. Research needs to be open to co-design with citizens and citizen science campaigns, which can be useful tools to engage the general public and communicate the research process. Research integrity and academic freedom were considered as crucial to promote trust in research and researchers. Panellists reiterated the need to better communicate about the ERA and to raise awareness about its existence and importance.

Conclusions

A series of overarching elements emerged from the discussions as essential for an effective ERA. These included cross-border collaboration, Open Science, research excellence, inclusiveness, cross-sectoral mobility, free circulation of researchers, interdisciplinarity, access to research infrastructure, and the links between science and society. All these areas are relevant for Science Europe, which is actively working on many of them.

Cross-border collaboration was highlighted as key to building capacity in less research-intensive regions, supporting researchers' mobility, and promoting scientific excellence across Europe. During the discussions, it was stressed that mobility had been profoundly changed by the pandemic, and that digital mobility and the appropriate infrastructure must be better supported. Science Europe will continue to investigate and discuss new strategies, tools, and related policies to support collaboration in an increasingly complex and interconnected global scientific ecosystem. One such activity co-ordinated by Science Europe is a bottom-up, cross-European initiative to support excellent collaborative research programmes across borders. The initiative, called '[Weave](#)', was mentioned during the discussions and will be launched in December 2020.

The importance of Open Science, including Open Access to research publications and the sharing and re-use of research data, was also reiterated during the discussions. Science Europe remains committed to achieve a sustainable transition to Open Access to ensure that research results and knowledge are freely accessible, including through supporting its members in adapting their policies and supporting tools. It was recognised that the COVID-19 pandemic has seen a surge in the application of Open Science, which now should be transformed into lasting and sustainable practice.

Moreover, the discussions tackled evolution trends in the research culture. It will be essential to develop a broader understanding of the research process, and to recognise and reward a wider range of contributions and skillsets than has been done so far. In this regard, Science Europe will implement an activity that will map national, European, and global initiatives related to research culture. Last but not least, the links between science and society need to be further explored for an effective ERA, both through reinforced interactions and communication between research and the general public, but also through harnessing science to address global challenges. It is essential that society understands that the research process, in its pursuit of knowledge, naturally deals with uncertainty. Science Europe will explore ways to improve the perception of science in and for society.

It is essential to create a level playing field for research and innovation across Europe and to meaningfully involve national governments, research organisations, and stakeholders such as Science Europe in the development and implementation of the relevant policies and the 14 new ERA Actions. As Commissioner Gabriel emphasised, the 'Pact for Research and Innovation' and the 'ERA Forum for Transition' will be key forum for multi-level collaboration. Science Europe and its members will continue to collaborate with each other and with the European Union to develop and implement ERA policies and programmes.

Science Europe members are developing and adapting national policies on an on-going basis to create the best possible conditions for research. Science Europe, in its role of providing support and co-ordination at European level, will take the conclusions of the High Level Workshop forward in its upcoming activities.

Programme

Wednesday 18 November 2020

09.00–09.15 Welcome speeches

- / **Marc Schiltz**, President of Science Europe
- / **Manuel Heitor**, Portuguese Minister for Science, Technology, and Higher Education

09.15–10.15 New Challenges for Research Mobility and Career Development in the ERA

Researcher mobility has been crucial for the flow of scholarly ideas and is at the heart of research collaboration. Researcher Mobility is nowadays standard practice to develop the careers of researchers and has become part of the research culture. This session will aim to identifying factors related to the current context of COVID-19 crisis and the transition towards sustainable environment that will influence the evolution of the research culture. It will also aim to identify new policies and practices needed to foster fair and efficient researcher mobility and career development.

Keynote speech

- / **Dame Ottoline Leyser**, UKRI's Chief Executive — with a focus on research culture

Panel discussion

- / **Ricardo Conde**, President of the Portugal Space Agency
- / **Rosa Menéndez**, President of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
- / **Miriam Van Hoed**, IDEA Consult (MORE4 study)

Moderation: **Angelika Kalt**, Director of SNSF, Switzerland

10.15–10.30 *Coffee break*

10.30–11.30 The European Research Area breaking the silos

This session will illustrate how openness and collaboration between research organisations is at the core of the European Research Area development, and crucial for the transition towards sustainable and resilient societies. Moreover, building on the experience and lessons learned from the response to COVID-19, it will explore policies to further support open science across disciplines and between academia, industry and society.

Keynote speech

- / **Helena Pereira**, President of the Board of Directors of FCT

Panel discussion

- / **Zbigniew Błocki**, Director of the Polish National Science Centre (NCN)
- / **Berthold Neizert**, Head of the Department of Research Policy and International Relations, Max Planck Society, Germany
- / **Thierry Damerval**, President of the French National Research Agency (ANR)

Moderation: **Ingrid Petersson**, Director General of FORMAS, Sweden

11.30–11.45 *Coffee break*

11.45–13.15 **High level panel discussion on research policies for a more resilient European society**

The objective of this session will be to identify key areas for action in the coming years and propose policy actions to enhance evidence-based EU policy-making related to resilience, crisis preparedness and response, as well as the research dimension of sectoral policies.

11.45–13.15 Round table discussion

- / **Mariya Gabriel**, European Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth
- / **Jure Gašparič**, State Secretary of Education, Science and Sport, Slovenia
- / **Karina Angelieva**, Deputy Minister of Science and Education, Bulgaria
- / **Dragoș Ciuparu**, State Secretary, Ministry of Education and Research, Romania
- / **Aase Marthe Hørrigmo**, State Secretary, Ministry of Research and Higher Education, Norway
- / **Martina Hirayama**, State Secretary for Education, Research and Innovation, Switzerland
- / **Barbara Weitgruber**, Director General for Scientific Research and International Relations, Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, Austria
- / **Wilfried Kraus**, Deputy Director General for European Cooperation at the Federal Ministry for Education and Research, Germany
- / **Manuel Heitor**, Minister for Science, Technology, and Higher Education, Portugal
- / **Marc Schiltz**, President of Science Europe

Moderation: **Lidia Borrell-Damián**, Secretary General of Science Europe

13.15–13.30 **Conclusions and Farewell**

- / **José Paulo Esperança**, Vice-President of the Board of Directors of FCT

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The ERA refers to a unified European Research Area in which researchers are free to move around, perform their research, and work together with researchers from other countries.

Creating the ERA requires the harmonisation of various rules, requirements, and regulations, and for closer international collaboration within the EU.

The High Level Workshop on ERA offers an annual platform for Science Europe Member Organisations, national ministries, and EU institutions to discuss progress, specific aspects, and future development of the ERA.